

THE MEANING OF THE CIRCLE AS A SYMBOL IN LITHUANIAN
FOLKLORE AND MYTHOLOGY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6546034>

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Abstract. *This article aims to convey the circles that connect the points of mythology and folklore. Each researcher has different insights into the circle because of lack of the theoretical studies, analyzes, results and summaries.*

Article relevance receives certain aspects of this scientific area. It is to identify the association between the circle and the circle point in mythology and folklore. A circle forms from cross spiral. And the circle is a round object. So, according to folklore, mythology noted that wheel, circle symbols and signs can be represented in with the cults, rituals, rites and customs. How these characters convey meaning, importantly, faced a crucial moment in human life as a guarantee of security with social and practical importance.

Keywords: *science fiction, circle, ritual, circular plant, folklore, sun, festival, customs.*

The symbol was important to the ancient people, by usage of it they expressed their feelings, their wishes and the annoyance. The symbol has always reached us in some way. Cultural connection between symbols and time periods - past, present and future still exist, only human attitudes and worldviews are changing. Human perception is changing in a way that can make it clear. The relevance of the article receives a special direction in the research: clarification of the circle and interaction between mythology and folklore. If we turn the cross, it will turn into circle.

The aspect of a circle and its symbolic meaning in Lithuanian folklore and mythology. The symbol of the circle in our custom means a typical symbol. Previously, the Lithuanian daily life was very modest, but featured with an aesthetic spring which surrounded by simple yet formed infallible objects. Relatives' ornaments and signs were reproduced on various objects, which told much of what our ancestors saw. The grandchildren inherited with the years of experience to protect and refurbish it. In this way, the distance keeps going through it strengthens human memory. The past was remembered through language, things, customs and image (Gaižutis 1992: 7).

At calendar festivals, some rituals and choreographic features may differ slightly: some jump, others move in a circle. The circle symbol which is chosen by us contains a holiday that rotates people rolling, hitting a cart and turning around the body are marked as changes in vitality. During the festivals items were used like Easter eggs and hub rolling which means spinning in a circle. The Easter Egg represents the model of the globe whereas hub - the symbol of the Sun movement. The fiery wheels or the hub that caused them to fall into the mountains, meant sunlight associated with the worship of the sun. The swirling movement is characterized by the Chinese New Year, Mardi Gras, St. George's Day, Easter and domes festivals. Motiejus Strijkovskis reports Dzidzis Lado in whose honor danced in circles. "Dzidis Lado - the great God, for whom" killed a snow-covered rooster. The festival ritual was held from May 25th to June 25th. They were played in a small house where girls and women danced and held circlets in hands, sang in a biting voice and repeated: lado, lado, lado, our great God. It is still used in Lithuania, Samogitia, Lithuania and Russia nowadays (BRMŠ II: 546). In Lithuanian ethnography, circles are interacted with agriculture and livestock. When the soil is ready for sowing, people circle around the fields and visit germinated crops that "magically ensure a good harvest" (Urbanavičienė 2000: 323327). In the harvest ritual, the end of the rye harvest at is a very important final bundle, cutting a handful around the world. From the same handful the owner makes a lattice and the rest makes a wreath. The owner or the coolest, or perhaps the youngest, reaper wears it on his head (Pretoria, BRMŠIII: 291). Matas Pretorijus wrote about this in as follows: "The nadruvians or skalvians prepare for the first time this kind of festival before the animals are grazed. Garden which is in front of the barn where he feeds the animals, walks around them three times while praying to God for protection of them" (BRMŠ III: 289).

In the fall, the shepherds fortune-tilled to finish grazing early. Catch the white goat and guide it around the birch so that it snows faster. They also called it snow. They took the goat in and led it around the birch tree three times. When it first snowed, they said: "The shepherds walked around the tree with the white goat" or they walked around the tree while walking the goat, and only guessed when the snow would start. After three laps around the tree, it will soon begin to snow. This ritual was used to expedite the end of grazing (OS2003: 247). Goats were sacrificed for the gods so that they could be reconciled when they became ill or had problems (BRMŠII: 282). Therefore, the Shepherd's Prophecy, which guides the goat around the birch, shows the importance of sacrifice to the well-known shepherd.

The circular plant, which part of it, forms the self-image of youth's life and nature. The symbolic representation of the letters is conveyed in folklore. World trees grow in the songs surrounding the mansion, such as the plane tree, oak and three linden trees. The plants and joys in the song are anthropomorphic and equal to the status of God, they are bred by sun and moon. A flower that rotates in a circle which is not circular, but it rotates, extends toward the sun, and blooms, so you may have the idea of a ring. The plant is mostly mentioned in the second joy. Circular roses treated in the form of circles and domes. People have created a classification of plants called roses. This is distinguished by the purity and brilliance of the flowers. This is highlighted by a song introduced by a girl who lived with her mother. At home, she was a virgin shaped by the pure desires: "*When I lived with my mom, I bloomed like a rose*". Bright roses, circles, dome-shaped shapes: dome-shaped rose circles, Ratileliai - plants leaves in a shape of round. In the dance, emotion has a bright narrative function and expresses the tendency to draw a circle. Glee is sung while Ratilelli dances, Ratilelli is bent, and the circle is bent: *ratilioj, bending circle, ratileli, lylio*. (Šeškauskaitė 2001: 56). The same circle as the curved circular Latileris corresponds to the tradition of the sacred circle of dancing and roaming.

In the world of mythology, one's own space is depicted in a circle that completely rotates around oneself, a living person or a dead person. Our own world, our own home, creates a unique space in a strange dead world. In folklore, the hero who escaped from a mythical creature draws in a circle. This is the way to resolve this conflict, where the protagonist receives the freedom of his choice and protects himself from death. Archaeological sources show a separation of living and dead, tied with garlands in the form of various tombs and burial mounds. This will create a room after death. Since the Bronze Age, stone garlands, three concentric stone garlands, then slabs, and cremation Baltic burials were used (Lithuanian Ethnogenesis 1987: 8688,104109). In the text and description of joy, the symbol of the circle and the dance in the circle in the life of her daughter-in-law while she lived in her husband's house laid the foundation for her different qualities. Every time you spin in the circle, it means some kind of ritual, and when you confirm it, your daughter-in-law was accepted by the family community. A comparison of the daughter-in-law with the joyful sun, when the people of Primitive Society perceive the universe as a powerful and mysterious force that controls and empowers everything, people and even the life of God. The ancients were closely associated with the circle's nature. In the glees, it became clear that the daughter-in-law's adherence to the circle ritual was an important affirmation of the

law. She walked around in a circle, sang, passed through raised hands, walks in a circle. All of this marked the creation of a space model at the place where she lived, her mother-in-law's house. The cosmic order revolves around the sun, the bearer of life on Earth, and its rays promote vegetation. Daughter-in-law's ritual differs in other respects, which rotates in a circle, passes through glees "What Flows Through the Manor", rolls wheels (circle), litingo/manor house, ritingo, where gifts are mentioned.

According to researchers' views, it is important to differ various meanings of the circle rotation. The circle is the oldest form of the Sun, and it is a sign that all Indo-Europeans share. A circle's symbolism is similar to that of the heavenly bodies: the sun, moon, and stars. Drawing a circle in sorcery, tying bands, pacing around the fireplace (table), circle (hub) rolling and sorcery, sieve spinning and sorcery, beer drinking (sipping) sending a glass in a circle are all classic folk symbolic actions. Incantations, games, and dances, as well as a circle, wandering around the garden, around the deceased, and incantations, games, and dances. The symbolism of a circle dance originated from the research of folklore literature and explanations of symbols. while the daughter-in-law lives with her husband. Daughters - inlaw ritual and validation to the tribe's community. Circle - rotation, dancing in a circle - daughters inlaw ritual and validation to the tribe's community.

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